

SOCIO-POLITICAL CONCEPTUAL SPHERE

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The effectiveness of applying the provisions of cognitive linguistics and semantics to the learning of terminology is explained by the fact that the term creation is directly related to the formation, storage, and transfer of scientific knowledge. Which means the work of mental structures that are embodied in linguistic signs of terminology. N.A. Slusareva emphasizes that in terminology the result of the cognitive process in this field of knowledge is fixed. While the terms serve for the conceptualization and classification of the knowledge. Therefore, to implement the procedure for identifying the semantic information of a term, such a concept is used as a representation, which serves as a quantitative unit of representation of surrounding reality in an individual's thoughts and replaces a certain part of the unreal-real world in reflective processes. It is important to note that the concept is considered part of a more general category: "conceptual system", "conceptual picture of the world", "conceptual model", and "concept sphere". At the same time, not only the conceptual picture of the world but also the conceptual sphere is characterized as a system of opinions and knowledge about the world, reflecting the cognitive experience of a person, the totality of all concepts, and their orderly unification. Nevertheless, "the concept of the concept sphere is especially important in that it helps to understand why language is not just a method of communication, but a kind of nation's culture and its embodiment in different segments of the population, down to an individual".

This view of the conceptual sphere makes it possible to define it as a meaningful outline of the world, taking into account the "interaction of such factors as national tradition and folklore, religion and ideology, life experience and examples of art, 00 by national-cultural, spiritual, and historical factors, in the form of a holistic image that is decomposed into components, or concepts. At the same time, the national language pictures the world as a linguistic-cultural model defined as a partial projection of the concept sphere, realizing some of its fragments in verbal form. As a rule, the conceptual sphere serves as the information base of the cognitive consciousness of a group of people and an individual. The main source of concept formation is the personal cognitive activity of man. It is obvious that there is a basic stereotypical core of knowledge, or the cognitive base of a people, that stands out from the individual

concept spheres as some part of them and is equally appropriated by all members of the lingual cultural community. Belonging to a certain culture is determined by the presence of a basic stereotypical core of knowledge, repeated in the processes of socialization of individuals in a given society, and the stereotypical (at the level of ethnic culture rather than personality) selection of peripheral elements. With this approach, the conceptual sphere of the people seems to justify the allocation of group conceptual spheres and scientific and professional conceptual spheres as well. Moreover, the socio-political conceptual sphere refers to a complex network of concepts or ideas that mediate social and political life. These concepts include ideas, theories, values, assumptions, and beliefs about how society is structured and functions. The socio-political conceptual sphere involves a framework of understanding the political world which shapes how people perceive, locate, and respond to specific social and political issues. These concepts describe social, cultural, and political systems, and as such play a significant role in shaping cultural norms, values, attitudes, and behaviours. The sphere also includes historical, economic, and geopolitical concepts as well as media's influence, which shape how individuals engage with political issues and society. Thus, individuals' understanding of these concepts significantly impacts their political orientation, opinions, and behaviour. It is crucial to understand the socio-political conceptual sphere as it helps individuals to analyze political and social issues, participate in political discussions, and make informed decisions as citizens. To understand the sphere, extensive knowledge of the context from which each concept arises is important.

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